

Emotional Response to a Picture by the Change of Color: a comparison study between adults and children

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate whether the emotional response to a picture varies with regard to the change of its color modes. Furthermore, it was examined whether the age difference, in particular, adults and children has an effect. In order to examine the influence of color mode on the emotional responses, picture stimuli were collected when their semantic contents were strongly attached to typical colors, i.e. memory colors. The International Affective Picture System (IAPS) was referred to collect emotionally normative pictures, and eight pictures were selected: two of each quadrant in emotion space defined by pleasure and arousal. The color modes of the pictures were processed into in monotone scales using memory color, gray, and complementary color of its memory color. In experiments, a set of pictures was shown to the subjects who were asked to assess their emotional responses in terms of Pleasure and Arousal using the Self-Assessment-Manikins (SAM). Two identical experiments were carried out with a group of university students and a group of elementary school children. Based on the SAM ratings of both subjects groups, it was revealed that the complementary color can elicit negative emotional responses to the picture that were previously categorized to induce the positive emotion. In addition, when the pictures were presented in grayscale, the emotional response in arousal dimension appeared to be lower. The emotional responses from children appear in a similar pattern as those from adults on Pleasure dimension ($p>0.05$, Twoway ANOVA). Regarding the emotional responses on Arousal, age difference effects, however no systematic explanation is yet provided.

Conference theme: Design & Emotion: Theoretical issues

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1. Introduction

As media technology has developed and it became more inexpensive to press colorful images on media, the impact of chromatic visual information drew a great attention. In comparison with achromatic visual information, chromatic one can contain richer and more realistic semantic contents. Therefore, many studies have advocated colorful information to improve the quality of cognitive information as well as emotional information. Gilbert and Schuhleuder (1990) insisted that chromatic photos can more transmit the semantic contents more efficiently than achromatic photos. In Detenber and his colleagues (2000)'s study, the subjects remembered achromatic movie clips better than chromatic ones. However, some raised questions whether the chromatic visual information would always enhance the quality of communication. On the other hand, Zettl (1990) asserted that the emotional response to achromatic film varies in a stronger pattern than that to chromatic one, since a person's attention is not distracted by Chroma information of the film. Also, Bradley and his colleagues (2001) obtained similar emotional responses from both colorful and achromatic photos. Based on this, Bradley and Lang (2007) suggested that achromatic photos should be better as emotion elicitor rather than colorful photos the color of that are incorrectly printed or displayed.

Therefore, the effect of Chroma has been often focused and the debates are concluded differently depending on their own empirical contexts. Moreover, previous studies compared the effect of Chroma and have not yet expanded the topic to the "right" or "wrong" color hue. For instance, a picture of a tomato may induce positive emotion. How it would be when a tomato appears in blue? Would this picture elicit still the positive emotion? Or would it evoke rather negative emotion? On the contrary, a picture with bleeding victim presented in grayscale could be seen less provocative than in original. It is not difficult to assume that the emotional response to a picture in unusual color would be influenced. For example, a blue tomato would not elicit appetite feeling. Instead, it could elicit even disgusting feeling, since people never (almost) experienced a blue tomato and food in blue is often inedible, perhaps except blue cheese. However, children might find it interesting, since their life experience is not yet enough to form typical color association.

In this study, we attempted to test the different emotional responses between adults and children. To give an example, when Heinz marketed variety colors of ketchup recipe, contrary to adults in a fright, children loved the green and violet ketchup. Besides, blue color that decreases an appetite is used for beverages for children. This recent tendency which breaks from fixed color is increasing rapidly. Particularly, because this case succeeded by applying complementary color of the product semantic color, we could get valuable leads to approach a new investigation about emotion response to a picture influenced by age.

In this way, we intended to investigate how people respond to pictures that are presented in “unusual color” and to reveal whether age effects. We tried to provide empirical evidence that explains the emotional responses to the right as well as wrong combination between the semantic content and color of the picture.

2. Emotional Response to Pictures

2.1 International Affective Picture System (IAPS)

In order to provide a set of normative emotional stimuli for experimental investigations of emotion and attention, the International Affective Picture System (IAPS) was developed by Lang and his colleagues in 1999. The aim of IAPS was to develop a large set of standardized, emotionally evocative, internationally accessible, color photographs that includes contents across a wide range of semantic categories (Lang, Bradley, Cuthbert, 1999). The database of pictures is continuously updated and there are 956 pictures available in the 2005 version. The affectivity of pictures has been assessed in terms of pleasure, arousal, and dominance for more than 15 years and more than 10,000 subjects joined to assess them. For an empirical study, we looked for pictures the semantic contents of that are typically associated with certain colors. For example a picture (IAPS number 7460) illustrates a handful of French fries and the typical color thereof is, in this case, brilliant yellow. In this way, we selected 8 pictures from each quadrant of emotion space that is defined by pleasure and arousal: The emotional profile of each quadrant is described as +pleasure/+arousal (1st quadrant), -pleasure/+arousal (2nd quadrant), -pleasure/-arousal (3rd quadrant), and +pleasure/-arousal (4th quadrant) respectively. The selected 8 pictures are presented in following Figure 1.

Figure 1. Eight IAPS picture stimuli

2.2 Memory Color

In this study, we adopt a term, memory color. According to Goldstein's definition, memory color is that, in which an object's characteristic color influences our perception of its color (Goldstein, 2002 p. 209). For example, the Image number 7 in Figure 1, a photo of earth has memory color of cobalt blue. We intended to examine how the emotional responses would change when the color of a picture changes from its memory color to the complementary color of the memory color. Therefore, the picture stimuli used in experiments are shown to the subjects after we manipulated the color in memory color, grayscale, or complementary color.

2.3 Age Difference in Emotional Response to IAPS Pictures

Henderson and Fox (2007) suggested that motor development and the emergence of fear come from their experience and learning in the process of infant and children's emotion development. Also, emotion does not develop in isolation, but rather, changes as a function of the interaction between an infant and physical and social environment. Thus, the children who have less social experience and knowledge than adults would exhibit different emotional response.

The pictures of IAPS have been admitted as affective stimuli for studying emotion in children because they do not rely on verbal or reading skills. Thus, Lang and his colleagues developed a

picture set suitable for viewing by children and compared ratings of pleasure, arousal, and dominance acquired from young children (7-9 years old) (Lang et al., 1999). A very similar relationship was found for the children. Strong positive correlations between the children's and adults' ratings were found for both pleasure and arousal, suggesting that children rated the pictures similarly to adults. Not the more, Backs, Silva and Han used Self-Assessment Manikin (SAM) ratings to examine whether groups of 21 younger (M age = 20.02 years, SD = 2.28) and 21 older (M age = 66.26 years, SD = 5.64) adults had similar affective experiences to pictures from the IAPS (2005). That is in contrast with that infants have different emotional change as acquiring complex emotion. It can be construed in such a way emotional response of children who have no problem in communication is similar to adults'.

3. Goals and Hypotheses

In this study, we intended to investigate how people emotionally respond to a color picture whose color is manipulated. Moreover, we tried to whether there is any age influence while assessing the emotional response to affective picture in unusual color (i.e. complementary color of memory color). Therefore, two hypotheses are formulated as follows.

[H. 1] The emotional response to affective picture is influenced by color manipulation.

[H. 2] The effect of [H 1.] in children appears in a different pattern from that in adults: Children find unusual usage of color interesting (i.e. more positive and more arousing).

4. Plan of Experiment

In order to examine the emotional responses to affective pictures the theme color of that were manipulated, we selected picture stimuli, manipulated their color based on the theme, and facilitated the Self-Assessment-Manikins (SAMs). Two identical experiments were conveyed with group of university students as well as with group of children.

4.1 Picture Stimuli

Image stimuli employed in the experiment were presented in Table 1. Initially, eight pictures were selected from the International Affective Picture System (IAPS). Their emotional profiles were characterized in terms of the dimensions of emotion, such as pleasure and arousal in a dichotomized way (+/-Pleasure; +/-Arousal). To maximize the emotional effect of pictures, some pictures were cropped and replaced with similar pictures containing similar contents. Finally, eight pictures were selected by an expert group comprised of four students in industrial design master course. The color modes of pictures were manipulated into 1) the memory color associated with semantic contents, 2) the complementary color of the memory color in HSB

color space, 3) the grayscale. Adobe Photoshop CS3 was used for image processing. And each image was comprised of 32 slides with Microsoft Power Point.

		Picture stimuli	
pleasant & arousing	original		
	memory		
	comple-mentary		
	grayscale		
un-pleasant & arousing	original		
	memory		
	comple-mentary		
	grayscale		
un-pleasant & de-activated	original		
	memory		
	comple-mentary		
	grayscale		
pleasant& de-activated	original		
	memory		
	comple-mentary		
	grayscale		

Table 1. 32 Picture Stimuli

4.2 Measurement of Emotion Response

Developed by Lang (1980) SAM is a nonverbal, culture-fair rating system based on a three dimensional system of emotion consisting of valence, arousal, and dominance. The SAM rating scale is comprised of three sets of graphic figures, respectively representing the three dimensions (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Self-Assessment-Manikin (SAM)

These graphic figures, which depict values along each of the three dimensions on a continuously varying scale, are used to indicate emotional reactions. As shown in Figure 2, SAM ranges from a frowning, unhappy figure to a smiling happy figure, when representing the valence dimension. For the arousal dimension, SAM ranges from a relaxed, sleepy figure to an excited, wide-eyed figure. For the dominance dimension, SAM ranges from a small figure (dominated) to a large figure (in control). The subject can select any of the five figures comprising each scale.

In this study, we focused on the emotional response on pleasure and arousal dimensions of emotion and thus the upper two rows in Figure 2 were facilitated in experiments.

5. Experiment I

5.1 Goal

The purpose of Experiment I was to investigate the influence of color mode on the emotional response of adults to pictures.

5.2 Method

5.2.1 Subjects

35 university students [M age= 20.97 years, SD=1.13] made up of 15 males and 20 females participated in experiment.

5.2.2 Stimuli

The 32 pictures presented in Table 1 were shown to the subjects in random order.

5.2.3 Procedure

The pictures were projected on a white screen with dimension of 2m width × 1.5m height. The experiment was conveyed in a lecture room with windows, but direct sunray was avoided. An experimenter assisted the slide show by checking each subject has finished the SAM assessment.

5.3 Results and Analysis

Among the 35 participants, we exempted two people since they failed to answer to several items. Accordingly, based on the SAM ratings of 33 subjects, a reliability test was performed. The Reliability Coefficients yielded a satisfactory level of internal consistency between independent variables (the SAM ratings): $\alpha=0.795$ in pleasure; $\alpha=0.732$ in arousal (on 32 variables) supporting that the picture stimuli with color manipulation were also appropriate as emotion elicitor. In following subsections, the SAM ratings of each IAPS picture were observed while its theme color of it was manipulated. The analysis is viewed according to the emotional profile of IAPS picture (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Four emotional profiles

5.3.1 Emotional Response to Color Manipulation of “pleasing and arousing” picture

The following Figure 4 and Figure 5 illustrate how the subjects rated their emotional response to the IAPS picture with a handful of French fries: As it was shown in original color, memory

color, complementary color, and grayscale. The Figure 4 shows that when the French fries were presented in complementary color (bluish) of the memory color (yellowish), the SAM ratings are smaller than 3, to be negative. Repeated Measurement Oneway ANOVA was conducted and provide statistical evidence that the mean difference in Figure 4 is significant ($F_{(3, 96)}=45.021$, $p<0.001$). As shown in Figure 5, in an aspect of arousal, the mean difference is less drastic than that in the Pleasure, but the difference is still statistically significant ($F_{(3, 96)}=12.817$, $p<0.001$). As indicated in the previous study (Suk, Jeong, Park, Park, & Chung, 2007), the picture stimuli in grayscale elicits less arousing emotion than colorful picture even when it is colored in an unusual way.

Figure 4. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (French fries) while its color is changing: Pleasure (N=33)

Figure 5. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (French fries) while its color is changing: Arousal (N=33)

5.3.2 Emotional Response to Color Manipulation of “unpleasing and arousing” picture

Second, we observe the SAM ratings of a picture of a burning man riding a bike. Regarding the responses in pleasure, as shown in Figure 6, the mean of SAM ratings changes to be “less” negative (unpleasant), and the mean difference while color manipulation is statistically significant (Repeated Measurement Oneway ANOVA, $F_{(3, 96)}=5.847$, $p=0.001$) at an alpha level of 0.05. However, the fluctuation in Figure 6 is much smaller than that in Figure 4. Figure 7 shows the averaged SAM ratings on arousal that illustrates that the activated emotion is reduced (neutralized) as the color mode is changed to be complementary or in grayscale ($F_{(3, 96)}=21.125$, $p<0.001$). Therefore, it replicates the tendency that the IAPS picture in grayscale elicits less arousing emotional response.

Figure 6. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (burning man) while its color is changing: Pleasure (N=33)

Figure 7. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (burning man) while its color is changing: Arousal (N=33)

5.3.3 Emotional Response to Color Manipulation of “unpleasing and deactivating” picture

Third, we again observe the trend that the negative affectivity is getting neutralized as the color of picture is manipulated (see Figure 8). The change of averaged SAM ratings is statistically significant ($F_{(3, 96)}=6.413, p=0.001$) as well. In an aspect of arousal, as the color is unusually used, such as complementary color or gray, the emotional responses were less activated (see Figure 9). The mean difference in this again significant ($F_{(3, 96)}=18.671, p<0.001$). Initially, we

expected that the subjects would rate their emotional responses to this IAPS picture of graveyard to be very calm. However, they evaluated it both in original and in memory color as slightly arousing (>3 in arousal). This indicates that the selection of picture stimuli should have been more careful in order to assure the characteristics of affectivity before color manipulation.

Figure 8. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (graveyard) while its color is changing: Pleasure (N=33)

Figure 9. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (graveyard) while its color is changing: Arousal (N=33)

5.3.4 Emotional Response to Color Manipulation of “pleasing and deactivating” picture

Last, we identify the characteristics of emotional response to pleasing and deactivating pictures. As explained in section 5.3.1, a pleasant picture elicits negative emotion ($<.3$ in pleasure) when it is colored in complementary color (see Figure 10). However, as the picture was shown in complementary color or in grayscale, it induced more arousing emotional responses than shown in original. The SAM ratings of a picture of dimming bulb, the other picture stimuli in the same emotional profile (4th quadrant), elicited the same pattern of arousing emotion. Repeated Measurement Oneway ANOVA was performed, and the mean differences are significant both in pleasure ($F_{(3,96)}=16.869, p<0.001$) and in arousal ($F_{(3,96)}=4.231, p=0.007$).

Figure 10. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (planet earth) while its color is changing: Pleasure (N=33)

Figure 11. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (planet earth) while its color is changing: Arousal (N=33)

6. Experiment II

6.1 Goal

In Experiment II, it was purposed to investigate the age difference in measuring the emotional responding to pictures in unusual color.

6.2 Method

6.2.1 Subjects

Experimenters visited an elementary school, and 31 elementary school children in 4th grade made up of 15 males and 16 females participated (M age=10, SD=0).

6.2.2 Stimuli

The picture stimuli of Experiment I used in Experiment II.

6.2.3 Procedure

The picture stimuli were displayed on a Projection Television in random order. Before the Experiment began, subjects were provided verbal instruction for using SAM.

6.3 Results and Analysis

Among 31 participants, we exempted 6 children, since they were not able to follow the instruction. Based on the SAM ratings of 26 subjects made up of 12 males and 14 females, we calculated Reliability Coefficients: $\alpha=0.690$ in pleasure; $\alpha=0.752$ in arousal. Therefore, we admitted that the 26 children's emotional responses were positively correlated in the satisfactory level.

Concerning statistical analysis, a mixed Twoway ANOVA was performed. The two factors and the tests thereof are presented in Table 2.

factor	test
color mode	Within-subjects contrasts
age group	Between-subjects effect

Table 2. Two main factors and the tests

Although we facilitated a Twoway ANOVA what interests us more is the factor, "age group", and thus the interaction effect between the two factors are not mentioned in this paper. In following subsections, the comparison analyses are discussed in terms of Pleasure and Arousal.

6.3.1 Emotional Responses on Pleasure

We conducted a mixed Twoway ANOVA using the SAM ratings of adults and children and the results are summarized in Table 3.

picture description	$F_{(1,57)}$	significance
French fries	3.180	p=0.016
burning man	2.883	p=0.095
graveyard	0.001	p=0.979
planet earth	0.133	p=0.717

Table 3. Effects of “age group” on between subject test, pleasure

As shown in Table 3, the influence of age difference was not significant, in 3 cases among 4, in emotional responses. This indicates that children assessed their emotional responses to three pictures, such as “burning man”, “graveyard”, and “planet earth” in a similar way to adults did while the colors were manipulated. However, the picture of French fries elicits different pattern of emotional responses between adults and children ($p < 0.05$). The following Figure 12 presents averaged SAM ratings of the picture of French fries comparing adults’ and children’s responses.

Figure 12. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (French fries) while its color is changing: a comparison between adults and children on Pleasure

Whereas adults evaluated the picture of French fries displayed in bluish color negative, children found it still positive. This may support the market support of unconventionally colored ketchups produced by Heinz. Furthermore, this remains a possibility of future study on children’s emotional responses to unusual food color.

6.3.2 Emotional Responses on Arousal

The SAM ratings of children on Arousal were compared with those of adults. We performed a mixed Twoway ANOVA in order to test whether the age group influenced on different patterns of emotional responses. As shown in Table 4, it is assumed that children rated the arousal emotion in a different way from adults did: The effect of “age group” is significant ($p < 0.05$) in viewing the three pictures, such as “French fries”, “graveyard”, and “planet earth”.

picture description	$F_{(1,57)}$	significance
French fries	4.689	$p=0.035$
burning man	0.005	$p=0.942$
graveyard	16.886	$p < 0.001$
planet earth	6.574	$p=0.013$

Table 4. Effects of “age group” on between-subject test, Arousal

In order to explain how different they are, we observed the following three charts: Figure 13, Figure 14, and Figure 15. In general, children felt more aroused than adults did. However, it is not yet conclusive to propose any systematic patterns of different emotional responses of children. We carefully predict that children feel excited or calm caused by different reasons from adults generally do.

Figure 13. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (French fries) while its color is changing: a comparison between adults and children on Arousal

Figure 14. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (graveyard) while its color is changing: a comparison between adults and children on Arousal

Figure 15. The SAM ratings of an IAPS picture (planet earth) while its color is changing: a comparison between adults and children on Arousal

7. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study attempted to investigate the color of a picture would influence the emotional response to the semantic contents of a picture. In experiment, eight were selected from IAPS, and each of them was modified in monotone scales using memory color, gray, and complementary color. Including the picture in original colors, the subjects were shown with 32

pictures in random order and assessed the emotional responses to each picture using the SAM. The experiment module was applied for a group of university students, representing an adult group, as well as a group of elementary school children.

In Experiment I (N=33), the SAM ratings are analyzed in aspects of the changes of emotional responses while the color modes of IAPS pictures are changed. A Repeated Measurement Oneway ANOVA provides statistical evidence that the SAM ratings are changing while the color mode varies supporting the [H. 1] ($p < 0.05$). In particular, the positive affectivity of pictures is easily damaged by color change. As positive pictures are colored in complementary colors, they elicit negative emotion. The results replicate the previous study of Suk and her colleagues (Suk et al., 2007). On the other hand, the complementary color can reduce negative affectivity of negative pictures. Regarding the emotional responses in arousal, there is a tendency that picture in grayscale is less arousing than chromatic pictures, including pictures colored in complementary colors.

In Experiment II (N=26), the SAM ratings were viewed focused on effects of age difference. Concerning pleasure, in general, adults and children felt in similar way ($p > 0.05$). As an exception, the evaluation of bluish French fries appears to be different: adults find it negative where as children does it positive.

In arousal, the age difference is found to be influential. However, it is not yet clear to conclude any systematic explanation. Therefore, the [H. 2] remains as an open question, and a further investigation is required.

As provided from the empirical study, color manipulation could be applied to enhance or weaken the emotional quality of affective pictures. To an extent, the different pattern of arousing response of children can be considered as a market opportunity. The current color marketing for food and beverage for children is dependent on adults' memory color and preference. Adults need to awaken children's imagination with various possibilities on applying colors, not to force to follow adults' inclination.

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